

05/17/2024 General news (Text: Claudia Hake/Franziska Peukert, Foto: Claudia Hake)

Perennial bed in front of the Central Library

A small bee paradise is being created on the lawn in front of the SUB Göttingen Central Library: in the newly created perennial bed there are over 400 drought-tolerant perennials on 50 square meters. The perennial plants, which will soon be in bloom, will serve as an additional source of food for wild bees and numerous other insect species. The [SUB's sustainability working group](#) initiated and coordinated the project.

For the bed, the area was excavated to a depth of 30 cm and filled with a perennial substrate. This ensures optimal conditions for the plants and minimizes the spontaneous appearance of weeds. Initially, the AG Nachhaltigkeit will water the plants daily until they have taken root, after which watering will no longer be necessary. A board with further information on the project and on animal and plant species will be set up near the bed for anyone interested.

The [Green Office](#) and Facility Management of the University of Göttingen, Michael Schwerdtfeger from the [Old Botanical Garden](#), the [Alumni Göttingen e. V.](#) and the the SUB Göttingen Hausdienste und Logistik worked closely together to ensure the successful implementation. Jasper Rasokat's concept of the [Ideas Competition for Students](#) was taken up for this. Some spontaneous helpers actively supported the planting.

The project was financed by the [City of Göttingen](#) and the [University Association](#). The Old Botanical Garden provided the plants.

Feel free to visit and observe the plants and their soon-to-arrive winged pollinators. We would ask you not to enter the bed for this purpose. Enjoy!

